

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

The influence of team work, working family conflict, working family conflict and work ability on the performance of members of the council of regional representatives of west Sumatra province

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Abstract

This study aims to see the effect of (1) team work on the performance of members of the Regional Representative Council (DPRD) of West Sumatra Province (2) Family work conflict on the performance of West Sumatra Province DPRD members (3) Occupational family conflicts on the performance of members of the Regional Representative Council of West Sumatra Province (4) Team work, Work-family conflict and work-family conflict jointly affect the performance of members of the Regional Representative Council of West Sumatra Province

The population and sample used were 65 people using a saturated sampling technique (census). The data analysis technique is multiple linear regression by fulfilling the classical assumption test requirements, namely the normality, multicollinearity and heteroscedasticity tests.

The results of this study indicate that (1) team work provide a significant positive influence on the performance of members of the Regional Representative Council of West Sumatra Province (2) Work family conflict has a significant negative effect on the performance of members of the Regional Representative Council of West Sumatra Province (3) Work family conflict has a significant negative effect on the performance of members of the West Sumatra Province DPRD (4) Team work, work family conflict and work family conflict jointly have a positive effect on the performance of members of the Regional Representative Council of West Sumatra Province.

Keywords: Performance; Team work; Work Family Conflict; Work Family Conflict

1. Introduction

Performance is the quantity and quality of the results of individual or group work within the organization in carrying out the main tasks and functions that are guided by norms, standard operating procedures, criteria and measures that have been set or that apply in the organization (Hasibuan, 2020). Based on this understanding, it can be concluded that the performance of the Regional Representative Council (DPRD) Members is used for the results of one's work in accordance with predetermined provisions, as well as their role in the organization within a certain period.

To achieve maximum performance, agencies must be able to create conditions that can encourage and enable DPRD Members to develop and improve their abilities and skills optimally. Basically the purpose of the organization is to improve performance to achieve organizational goals, to be able to survive in competition with other companies, and to achieve profit targets (Robbins, 2019).

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Organizations, companies or agencies are a collection of people who are managed or run by individuals or jointly who need large capital aimed at achieving the goals of the organization which are assisted in managing their business by DPRD Members.(Sinambela, 2018). Therefore, between company leaders and DPRD members, they must work well and solidly together, regardless of position level, so that the expected company goals can be achieved optimally.

The achievement of the goals of an agency is highly guided by the potential of human resources owned by each member of the DPRD. Therefore, agencies must have good human resource management because human resource management is not only a strategic activity, but also something that is essential in achieving organizational goals. In an organization, human resources have an important role. Its position is far from being just a means of production and driving organizational activities, human resources have a share in determining the progress or development of an organization.(Sutrisno, 2019).

The Regional People's Representative Council has three functions, namely:

- Legislation, relating to the formation of regional regulations
- Budget, Authority in terms of regional budget (APBD)
- Oversight, Authority to control the implementation of local regulations and other regulations as well as local government policies

DPRD has the right of interpellation, the right of inquiry, and the right to express opinions. DPRD members have the right to submit draft regional regulations, ask questions, submit suggestions and opinions, vote and be elected, defend themselves, immunity, attend orientation and study of duties, protocol, as well as finance and administration. DPRD has the right to ask state officials at the regional level, regional government officials, legal entities or members of the public to provide information. If this request is not complied with, a forced summons may be imposed (according to statutory regulations). If this forced summons is not fulfilled without a valid reason, the person concerned can be held hostage for a maximum of 15 days (according to statutory regulations).

The following is a table of targets and realization of the performance of DPRD members of West Sumatra Province in 2020-2022:

Table 1 Target and Realization of the Performance of DPRD Members of West Sumatra Province

No.	Performance Indicator	Realization 2020 (%)	Realization 2021 (%)	Realization 2022 (%)
1.	Implementation of DPRD Member Recess in 1 year	83	77	72
2.	Regional regulation issuance and discussion program in West Sumatra Province	81	80	79
3.	Dissemination of Regional Regulations to the People of West Sumatra Province	62	60	59
4.	Meetings - Work meetings with partners of each AKD (tools of the Board)	73	72	71

Source: West Sumatra Provincial DPRD Performance Report

If seen from the table above, the realization of the work program of the DPRD of West Sumatra Province has lasted The last 3 (years) did not reach the target. In 2022 indicators First of the planned target of 100% only achieved by 72%. On indicators second although the achievement was quite high at 79% but still did not reach the target. Likewise with indicators third which was targeted at 100% but only reached 59%. It can be said that on average the performance achievement of DPRD members of West Sumatra Province is only 71%. From these results it can be concluded that there are performance problems for DPRD Members because the realization does not reach the target. The decline in the performance of members of the DPRD of West Sumatra Province is thought to be influenced by several factors. Factors that are thought to influence this performance, such as team work, work-family conflict and work-family conflict.

Team work can be interpreted as teamwork or collaboration, team work or teamwork is a form of group work with complementary skills and is committed to achieving pre-agreed missions to achieve common goals effectively and efficiently(Wexley, 2020). It must be realized that teamwork is a fusion of various individuals who become one person to achieve a common goal. A team really needs a willingness to work hand in hand with each other. It could be that one

person does not complete work or is not skilled at job A, but can be done by other team members. This is what is meant by teamwork, the burden is shared for a common goal and complement each other.

According to Netemeyer et al, (2017) there are two types of dual role conflict, namely work-family conflict or Work-Family Conflict (WFC) and family-work conflict or Family-Work Conflict (FWC). Netemeyer et al, (2017) defines WFC as a form of conflict between roles including, demands, time, and tension that comes from work interfering with someone in carrying out their responsibilities in the family. For example, the obligation from the agency to members to continue their education abroad, makes these members have to leave their families. Another example of WFC is that a company requires members to work overtime on national holidays, making these members unable to gather with their families and enjoy holidays together. (Mian et al, 2019).

Another factor that is thought to influence the performance of DPRD members is work ability. Abilities and skills play an important role in individual work behavior and motivation. According to Handoko, (2019) ability is a trait that is born or learned that allows someone to complete his work, both mentally and physically. Members in an organization are well motivated, but not all have the ability to work well. Abilities and skills play a major role in individual behavior and performance. Skills are skills related to tasks that are owned and used by someone at the right time.

Based on the description of the background above, the researcher is interested in conducting research with the title "The Influence of Team Work, Work-Family Conflict, Work-Family Conflict and Work Ability on the Performance of DPRD Members of West Sumatra Province"

2. Materials and Methods

The population is the entire object of study which provides an accurate description of the research. According to Siregar, (2019) population is the total number of objects or subjects used as data sources in a study that have the same nature or characteristics. Thus, the population in this study were all 65 members of the DPRD of West Sumatra Province.

The research sample is a limited number and part of the population, a portion of the population that is selected and represents that population (Now, 2021). Meanwhile according to Sugiyono, (2017) the sample is part of the number and characteristics possessed by the population and what is learned from the sample, the conclusions will be applicable to the population. However, because the sample used is the entire population, namely the DPRD of West Sumatra Province, the sample in this study is the same as the population, namely the entire DPRD of West Sumatra Province, totaling 65 people.

The technique in taking this sample uses a total sampling technique (overall sample), total sampling is a sampling technique where the number of samples is equal to the population Sugiyono, (2017). The reason for taking total sampling is because according to Sugiyono, (2017) the total population is less than 100, the entire population is used as a research sample.

Testing the hypothesis in this study using multiple linear regression analysis. Multiple linear regression analysis aims to determine the causal relationship between the influencing variables and the affected variables. With the multiple regression equation model as follows:

$$Y = a + b_1 X_1 + b_2 X_2 + b_3 X_3 + + b_4 X_4 + + e \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Where:

- Y = Performance
- a = Intercept constant
- X1 = *Team work*
- X2 = WFC
- X3 = FWC
- X4 = work ability
- b1, ..., b4 = Regression Coefficient
- e = Error Term

3. Results

3.1. Classical Assumption Test Results

3.1.1. Normality Test Results

A good regression model is having a normal or close to normal residual distribution. The normality test used in this study is the One Sample Kolmogorof Smirnov test. This can be seen by comparing the value of asymp.sig (2 tailed) with a significant level of 5%. If asymp.sig (2 tailed) > 0.05 then the data is normally distributed, but otherwise the data is not normally distributed. The normality test results can be seen in table 2.

From table 2 it can be seen clearly, from the results of the normality test the asymp.sig value (2 tailed) is 0.657 > 0.05, so it can be concluded that the data in this study are normally distributed and meet the prerequisites of the classical assumption test.

Table 2 One-Sample Kolmogorov-Smirnov Test

		Unstandardized Residuals
N		65
Normal Parameters, b	Means	.0000000
	std. Deviation	8.738392
Most Extreme Differences	absolute	.054
	Positive	.045
	Negative	-.054
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		.849
asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		.657
a. Test distribution is Normal.		
b. Calculated from data.		

Source: Processed primary data, 2023

3.2. Multicollinearity Test Results

This multicollinearity test is needed to determine whether there are independent variables that have similarities with other independent variables in one model. A good regression model should not have a correlation between the independent variables. To detect symptoms of multicollinearity, identify the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) value. A common cut-off value to indicate the presence of multicollinearity is a tolerance value ≤ 0.10 or the same as a VIF value ≥ 10 . If a tolerance value ≥ 0.10 or the same as a VIF value ≤ 10 means that there is no multicollinearity between variables in the regression model. Based on the results of data processing that has been done, a summary of the results is shown in table 3.

Table 3 Multicollinearity Test

Variable	Collinearity Statistics	
	tolerance	VIF
Team work	0.637	1,569
WFC	0.923	1,083
FWC	0.537	1862
Work ability	0.521	1,850

Source: Processed primary data, 2022

In Table 3 it can be seen that each independent variable has a tolerance value of > 0.10. While the value of Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) < 10 so it can be concluded that team work, WFC, FWC, and work ability are free from multicollinearity symptoms so that further data processing stages can be implemented immediately.

3.3. Heteroscedasticity Test Results

The heteroscedasticity test aims to test whether in the regression model there is an inequality of variance and residuals from one observation to another. To test whether there is heteroscedasticity or not, you can use the Glejser test. If the probability is known to be above the alpha confidence level of 0.05, it can be concluded that there is no heteroscedasticity. The test results can be seen in table 4.

Table 4 Glejser test

Variable	Sig.
Team work	0.220
WFC	0.785
FWC	0.107
Work ability	0.325

Source: Processed primary data, 2022

From table 4 it can be seen that the effect of team work, WFC, FWC and work ability on the residual has a significance value of > 0.05, so it can be concluded that all variables do not have heteroscedasticity.

3.4. Hypothesis Test Results

3.4.1. Results of Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Multiple regression analysis is used to determine the regression coefficient of the independent variable and how it influences the dependent variable. It can be seen from the analysis of multiple regression data obtained using the SPSS Version 23 program as shown in table 5.

Based on the regression results from Table 5, it can be determined that the multiple linear regression equation in this study is as follows:

$$Y = 7.322 + 0.419X_1 - 0.476X_2 - 0.222X_3 + 0.277X_4$$

Table 5 Research Variable Multiple Linear Regression Results

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	std. Error	Betas		
1	(Constant)	7.322	3.091		2.368	0.019
	Team work	0.419	0.131	0.286	3.203	002
	WFC	-0.476	0.113	-0.384	-4.207	0.000
	FWC	-0.222	0.094	-0.159	-2.377	0.018
	Work ability	0.277	0.050	0.551	5.455	0.000
a. Dependent Variable: DPRD Member Performance						

Source: Processed primary data, 2023

The interpretation of the regression equation obtained is as follows:

- A constant of 7.322 states that if the variables team work (X1), WFC (X2), FWC (X3) and work ability (X4) are considered constant or ignored, then the performance of members of the DPRD of West Sumatra Province is 7.322 one-unit.
- The regression coefficient for team work (X1) is 0.419, meaning that if the other independent variables have a fixed value and team work has increased by 1 unit weight, then the performance of members of the DPRD of West Sumatra Province will increase by 0.419, and vice versa. The positive coefficient means that team work has a positive effect on the performance of DPRD members of West Sumatra Province.
- The regression coefficient of WFC (X2) is -0.476, meaning that if the other independent variables have a fixed value and the WFC increases by 1 unit weight, then the performance of DPRD members of West Sumatra Province will decrease by -0.476, and vice versa. The negative coefficient means that the WFC has a negative effect on the performance of members of the DPRD of West Sumatra Province.
- The regression coefficient of FWC (X3) is -0.222, meaning that if the other independent variables have a fixed value and FWC increases by 1 unit weight, then the performance of members of the DPRD of West Sumatra Province will decrease by -0.222, and vice versa. A negative coefficient means that FWC has a negative effect on the performance of DPRD members of West Sumatra Province.
- The regression coefficient of work ability (X4) is 0.277 meaning that if the other independent variables have a fixed value and work ability increases by 1 unit weight, then the performance of DPRD members of West Sumatra Province will increase by 0.277, and vice versa. The positive coefficient means that work ability has a positive effect on the performance of DPRD members of West Sumatra Province.

3.5. t test results (partially)

Hypotheses 1, 2 and 3 in this study were tested for validity using a partial test. The test is carried out by looking at the significance level (p-value), if the significance level resulting from the calculation is below 0.05 then the hypothesis is accepted, conversely if the calculated significance level is greater than 0.05 then the hypothesis is rejected.

- The influence of team work on the performance of DPRD members of West Sumatra Province

From the research results obtained a regression coefficient of 0.419 and the value of $t_{count} > t_{table}$ ($3.203 > 1.976$) with a significance of $0.002 < \alpha 0.05$, then H1 is accepted. It can be concluded that team work has a positive and significant effect on the performance of DPRD members of West Sumatra Province. That is, the higher the team work, the performance of DPRD members of West Sumatra Province will increase. Conversely, the lower the team work, the lower the performance of members of the West Sumatra Provincial DPRD.

- The influence of WFC on the performance of DPRD members of West Sumatra Province

The results showed that the regression coefficient was 0.476 and $t_{count} > t_{table}$ ($-4.207 > 1.976$) with a significance of $0.000 < \alpha 0.05$, then H2 is accepted. It can be concluded that WFC has a negative and significant effect on the performance of DPRD members of West Sumatra Province. That is, the higher the WFC, the lower the performance of DPRD members of West Sumatra Province. On the other hand, the lower the WFC, the lower the performance of members of the DPRD of West Sumatra Province.

- The influence of FWC on the performance of DPRD members of West Sumatra Province

The results showed that the regression coefficient was 0.222 and $t_{count} > t_{table}$ ($-2.377 > 1.976$) with a significance of $0.018 < \alpha 0.05$, then H3 is accepted. It can be concluded that FWC has a negative and significant effect on the performance of DPRD members of West Sumatra Province. That is, the higher the FWC, the lower the performance of members of the DPRD of West Sumatra Province. On the other hand, the lower the FWC, the lower the performance of DPRD members for West Sumatra Province.

- Effect of work ability on the performance of DPRD members of West Sumatra Province

The results showed that the regression coefficient was 0.277 and $t_{count} > t_{table}$ ($5.455 > 1.976$) with a significance of $0.000 < \alpha 0.05$, then H4 is accepted. It can be concluded that work ability has a positive and significant effect on the performance of DPRD members of West Sumatra Province. That is, the higher the ability to work, the performance of

DPRD members of West Sumatra Province will increase. Conversely, the lower the ability to work, the performance of DPRD members of West Sumatra Province decreases.

3.6. F Test Results (Jointly)

The F statistical test basically shows whether all the independent variables included in the model have a joint effect on the dependent or dependent variable (Sugiyono, 2013: 257). Based on the results of data processing that has been done, a summary of the results is obtained as shown in table 6.

Table 6 F Test Results

Model		Sum of Squares	df	MeanSquare	F	Sig.
1	Regression	5536398	4	1845,466	49.008	0.000b
	residual	5271928	60	37,657		
	Total	10808.326	64			
a. Dependent Variable: Y						
b. Predictors: (Constant), X1, X2, X3, X4						

Source: Processed primary data, 2023

Table 6 shows the value of $F_{count} > F_{table}$ ($49.008 > 3.06$) with a significance of $0.000 < 0.05$ (alpha), then H_5 is accepted. This means that the variables team work, WFC, FWC and work ability together have a significant effect on the performance of DPRD members of West Sumatra Province.

3.7. Determination Coefficient Test Results

The Coefficient of Determination Test (R^2) aims to see the magnitude of the influence of the independent variables on the dependent variable. The R^2 value ranges from 0-1, the closer to 0 the weaker the effect, whereas the closer to 1 the stronger the effect. The results of the analysis using R^2 range from 0-1, the closer to 0 the weaker the effect, whereas the closer to 1 the stronger the effect can be seen in table 7.

Table 7 Coefficient of Determination

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.716	0.512	0.502	6.136
a. Predictors: (Constant), FWC, Team work, WFC, Work ability				

Source: Processed primary data, 2022

From Table 7, the value of the adjusted R square shows 0.502, this indicates that the contribution of the variables team work, WFC, FWC and work ability to the performance of DPRD members of West Sumatra Province is 50.2% while 49.8% is determined by other factors that are not examined in this study such as organizational image, communication, work motivation, leadership style and so forth.

4. Discussion

Discussion of research results is intended to explain and interpret research results.

4.1. Influence Team work on the Performance of DPRD Members of West Sumatra Province

The results of this study indicate that team work has a significant positive effect on the performance of DPRD members of West Sumatra Province. This indicates that team work determines the performance of DPRD members of West Sumatra Province. This means that the higher and stronger the teamwork that exists for DPRD members in agencies, the performance of DPRD members will improve.

From the results of this study, it appears that variable *team work* has a coefficient of 0.419 which means that team work has the second largest influence. This indicates that team work has an impact on improving the performance of DPRD members. If the DPRD of West Sumatra Province wants to improve the performance of DPRD members, then the leadership must activate team work.

The results of this study are in accordance with income Wigiadi and Sunyoto, (2017), which states that team work is a form of group work with complementary skills and is committed to achieving a pre-agreed mission to achieve common goals effectively and efficiently.

The results of this study are in line with research conducted by A.Aji Tri Budianto and Amelia Katini, in the Scientific Journal of Management Volume 3, Number 1 with the title "The Influence of Team Work on Employee Performance at PT Perusahaan Gas Negara (PERSERO) Tbk SBU Distribution Region I Jakarta " which concluded that team work has an effect on employee performance, attitudes and behavior of employees who are friendly to others and more improved in order to motivate employees to improve performance. Team work must also be the concern of leaders where lighting that is too bright, air circulation and the atmosphere of team work can affect employee comfort and performance. The results of this study are also in accordance with Asti, (2017) on the team work variable has a significant effect on employee performance. This is marked by a significant value, which means there is influence and is positive (significant).

4.2. Influence WFC on the Performance of DPRD Members of West Sumatra Province

The results of this study indicate that WFC has a significant negative effect on the performance of DPRD members of West Sumatra Province. This indicates that the WFC determines the performance of DPRD members of West Sumatra Province. This means that the higher the WFC occurs in agencies, the lower the performance of the DPRD members will be.

From the results of this study, it appears that the WFC variable has a coefficient of -0.476 which means WFC has the greatest influence of other variables. This indicates that the WFC has proven to significantly reduce the performance of DPRD members. If the DPRD of West Sumatra Province wants to improve the performance of DPRD members, it must be able to overcome the WFC situation of DPRD members in agencies.

The results of this study are in accordance with the opinion Greenhaus, JH and Beutell, (2017), which states that WFC is a form of inter-role conflict, namely role pressure from work and role pressure from the family which contradict each other in several respects. That is, that carrying out roles in the family becomes more difficult because of the distraction from the role at work.

The results of this study are in accordance with the research Afzal, Sidia and Yasir, (2014) examine the effect of WFC on employee performance. The influence between WFC on performance is negative. This means that the higher the work-family conflict (WFC) experienced by employees, the lower their performance. Conversely, when the work-family conflict (WFC) experienced by employees is low, their performance will increase. This is in accordance with research Namasivayam, (2019), which reveals, that WFC has a negative effect on performance. Similar to the aforementioned research, research Carr, et al, (2017); Zhao, (2019); as well as Rathi, (2018) also stated, that WFC has a negative influence on performance.

4.3. Influence FWC on the Performance of DPRD Members of West Sumatra Province

The results of this study indicate that FWC has a significant negative effect on the performance of DPRD members of West Sumatra Province. This indicates that the FWC determines the performance of DPRD members of West Sumatra Province. This means that if the FWC of DPRD members increases in an institution, it will result in a decrease in the performance of DPRD members.

From the results of this study, it appears that the FWC variable has a coefficient of -0.22 which means FWC has the smallest influence of other variables. This indicates that FWC can have an impact on decreasing the performance of DPRD members. If the DPRD of West Sumatra Province wants to improve the performance of DPRD members, then they must be able to control FWC on DPRD members.

The results of this study are in line with the opinion Baggers, (2017) FWC is conflict originating in the family that interferes with work responsibilities. For example, a worker is late for work because he has to take his child to a daycare first. Karimi, (2017) examine the relationship of FWC (family-work conflict) with the outcome variable, namely performance.

This is also in accordance with the results of research from Rathi, (2018); Karimi, (2017) which states, that the FWC variable has a negative effect on performance. This means that when an employee feels high family-work conflict (FWC), it will result in decreased performance. When the family-work conflict (FWC) experienced by employees is low, their performance will be high.

4.4. Influence work ability on the Performance of DPRD Members of West Sumatra Province

The results of this study indicate that work ability has a significant positive influence on the performance of DPRD members of West Sumatra Province. This indicates that work ability determines the performance of DPRD members of West Sumatra Province. This means that if the work ability of DPRD members increases in an institution, it will result in improving the performance of DPRD members.

From the results of this study, it appears that the working ability variable has a coefficient 0.277 which means that work ability has a small influence from other variables. This indicates that work ability can have an impact on improving the performance of DPRD members. If the DPRD of West Sumatra Province wants to improve the performance of DPRD members, then they must be able to increase the work ability of DPRD members.

The results of this study are in line with the opinion (Bagger, 2017) work ability is a conflict originating in the family that interferes with work responsibilities. For example, a worker is late for work because he has to take his child to a daycare first. Karimi, et al. (2012) examined the relationship between FWC (family-work conflict) and the outcome variable, namely performance.

This is also in accordance with the results of research from Rathi, (2018); Karimi, (2017) which states, that the FWC variable has a negative effect on performance. This means that when an employee feels high family-work conflict (FWC), it will result in decreased performance. When the family-work conflict (FWC) experienced by employees is low, their performance will be high.

4.5. Influence Team work, WFC, and FWC on the performance of DPRD members of West Sumatra Province

The results of this study indicate that team work, WFC, FWC jointly have a significant influence on the performance of DPRD members of West Sumatra Province. This indicates that team work, WFC, FWC determine the performance of DPRD members of West Sumatra Province. This means team work, WFC, FWC, it will reduce the performance of DPRD members.

This is in line with research (Namasivayam, 2019), (Carr, et al 2017), (Zhao, 2019) which shows that the results show support for a significant influence between team work, WFC, FWC on the performance of DPRD members.

5. Conclusion

Based on the results of the testing and discussion of the hypotheses described in the previous chapter, several conclusions can be drawn as follows:

- *Team work* has a positive influence on the performance of DPRD members of West Sumatra Province. This means that the performance of DPRD members will increase if team work can also be improved. Thus the first hypothesis (H1) is accepted.
- WFC has a negative influence on the performance of DPRD members of West Sumatra Province. This means that the performance of DPRD members will increase if the WFC can be reduced. Thus the second hypothesis (H2) is accepted.
- FWC has a negative influence on the performance of DPRD members of West Sumatra Province. This means that the performance of DPRD members will increase if the FWC of DPRD members can be managed and reduced. Thus the third hypothesis (H3) is accepted.
- Work Ability has a negative influence on the performance of DPRD members of West Sumatra Province. This means that the performance of DPRD members will increase if the Work Capabilities of DPRD members can be managed and reduced. Thus the third hypothesis (H4) is accepted.
- *Team work, WFC, FWC* jointly have an influence on the performance of DPRD members of West Sumatra Province. From the ANOVA test, a significance probability value of 0.000 is obtained. The significance probability is less than 0.05, with a significance level of 0.000 as a result H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted. The variables team work, WFC, FWC jointly affect the performance of DPRD members of West Sumatra Province.

- Based on the results of the discussion analysis and some conclusions in this study, suggestions that can be given through the results of this study in order to get better results, namely:
- For team work, it is suggested to agencies to be able to pay attention to the team work of DPRD members in agencies, because this can be seen from the survey results and the results of respondents' responses to team work, showing poor results. DPRD members which will affect the performance of agencies.
- For WFC, it is suggested to agencies to be able to provide a balance in the world of work with the family world of DPRD members. Such as setting the working hours of DPRD members so that DPRD members do not lose time with their families.
- For FWC, the leadership and all DPRD members must be able to create working conditions that can reduce the FWC of DPRD members. Because, if left unchecked, this condition will worsen the performance of DPRD members of West Sumatra Province by providing relevant working time.
- For future researchers, it is hoped that they can examine other variables outside of this variable in order to obtain more varied results which can describe what things can affect performance and it is recommended to be able to reduce the influence of team work, WFC, FWC on the performance of DPRD members who used in this research.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Disclosure of conflict of interest

All authors contributed positively to the writing of this manuscript and there no conflict of interest as agreed to the content of this research.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individuals respondents included in the study.

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